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INCLUSIVENESS OF NEURODIVERSE STUDENTS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION CURRICULUM DESIGN AND DELIVERY

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Motivation: Research shows that 15-20% of the population suffers from conditions that are classed as neurodiverse [1]. Wikipedia defines neurodiversity as “an approach to learning and mental health that argues various neurological conditions are the result of normal variations in the human genome” [2]. In this approach ADHD, Autism, Depression, and Dyslexia and other neurological conditions are framed as natural human variations and are an authentic form of diversity, self-expression and being with the rights to be allowed to live their lives as they are just like neurotypicals.

Evidence has showed that in engineering degrees neurodiverse students are overrepresented [3].

Neurodiverse people benefit from more awareness and support in their education. Their intellectual abilities are generally high to excellent. The problem in engineering education appears to occur in areas relating to transversal and organizational skills and the mismatched expectations of educational institutions. As a result, neurodiverse students are more likely to drop out [4] [5].

Rationale: The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) [6], obliges universities to ensure a proactive, inclusive educational environment; a reactive support network is no longer sufficient. Many universities in Europe have support networks in place, but not many universities train education staff in how to take into accounts the needs of students in curriculum design and delivery. Yet lecturers and curricula developers must also play their part in inclusivity. However, there is a lack of awareness among lecturers and curricula developers what it means to be neurodiverse in a Higher Education environment, let alone that they are aware of the, often practical, needs of neurodiverse students in terms of course set up and delivery.

Participant engagement: Participants will debate statements on adaptation and inclusivity in curriculum design and delivery with aim to create awareness of the needs of neurodiverse students. After that, participants take part in brain storm session coming up with creative solutions to problems commonly experienced by neurodiverse

students. The participants will be divided in smaller groups and discuss issues a neurodiverse student may run into. It is endeavored to introduce real problems from the perspective of real (anonymous) neurodiverse students. At the end of the workshop each group reports back with their solution which will also be included in the proceedings. There is no limit to the number of people that can take part. Everyone is welcome.

Takeaway: This workshop will provide educators with concrete information and inspiration to create a more inclusive engineering education for neurodiverse students. The results of the workshop will be included in the conference proceedings.

Significance for engineering education: By creating more neurodiverse friendly engineering education, overall student retention and success will go up, not only among neurodiverse students. This workshop will enhance understanding of the needs of neurodiverse students, the challenges they face and the importance of taking their needs into account when designing the inclusive engineering education.

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Inclusiveness of Neurodiverse Students in Engineering Education Curriculum Design and Delivery

Workshop

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Programme

- Introduction
- Agree or Disagree?
- Neurodivergent vs. Neurotypical
- Pyramid of Inclusive Education
- Making your education Inclusive
- Main Takeaways
- Afterthought

Do you agree?

“A student cannot become an engineer if they cannot write a thesis without help.”

TU Delft

Do you agree?

“A student won't get half an hour extra in industry”

TU Delft

Do you agree?

“If a student cannot work in teams they can never be a good engineer.”

TU Delft

Do you agree?

“I don't want to supervise student who talk too much and go off on tangents all the time. They are so tiresome.”

TU Delft

Do you agree?

“Students who cannot spell do not belong at university.”

What is Neurodiversity?

The diversity of human brains and minds – the infinite variation in neurocognitive functioning within our species.

[source: neurocosmopolitanism.com]

What is Neurotypical?

Having a style of neurocognitive functioning that falls within the dominant societal standards of “normal”.

[source: neurocosmopolitanism.com]

What is Neurodivergence?

Having a brain that functions in ways that diverge significantly from the dominant societal standards of “normal”.

[source: neurocosmopolitanism.com]

Some Possible Forms of Neurodivergence

[Source: suelarkey.com.au]

Issues for Neurodivergent Students

First of all: Everyone's form of neurodivergence is **different**, however they do share **common problems** in education:

- **Different way of processing** -> Often require more time for processing,
- **Losing sight of objective** -> Do not finish, go off on tangents
- **Time & Self Management** -> Late, unstructured ways of working, can't synthesize
- **Understanding Expectation** -> Especially when requirements are very open
- **Prioritizing** -> Distinguishing between major and minor issues
- **Interpreting differently**-> Misinterpreting questions/explanation or social situation
- **Sensory Overload** -> Getting emotional or withdrawing
- **Anxiety** -> Unfamiliarity or unpredictability of situation/people

As a result

Neurodivergent students have a high risk of dropping out in education due to low self confidence, fear of failure and anxiety

In Engineering Education

*Neurodivergent students are overrepresented:
Autism: 4 times more likely
Similar suspicions exist for ADHD
and Dyslexia*

[source: Meester & Draaijer, 2014]

Why should we treasure neurodivergent students?

Why not?

- Everyone is entitled by law to the same chances for success regardless of their disability, based on the UN Convention for the Rights of People with a Disability
- But more importantly, we would be wasting enormous talents as neurodivergent students also bring many positive traits with them,

Such as:

- Creativity
- Analytical Skills
- Problem Solving Skills
- Thinking out-of-the box
- Enthusiasm, Drive and Passion
- Trouble shooting
- Ability to foresee problems
- Great eye for detail, etc..

What is inclusive education?

Expressed scientifically:

When the Normalized Standard deviation: $\bar{\sigma} = 0,5$

Pyramid of Inclusive Education

Universal Design for Learning

[source: www.ahead.ie]

Your Assignment

In groups:

- Pick an issue a neurodivergent student may face in engineering education and brainstorm on possible solutions
- Report back to plenary with your issue and your possible solutions
- Feel free to include solutions already in place at your institution

What is your Main Take Away for Today?

Please write on a card

- On one side: your main takeaway
- On the other side: what improvement you will make in the way you teach or interact with (neurodiverse) students

And take it with you!

Main Outcomes

Based on Discussion during Workshop

- Neurodiversity is an important subfamily within diversity in engineering education
- The SEFI WG on Diversity will look at how they can also ensure neurodiversity is included in their WG topics
- It is important to understand that neurodiverse students (and staff) look at things differently and therefore it is important to check that teaching methods and the way information is shared does not hinder these students in their studies
- The pyramid of Inclusive Education can be a useful tool to raise awareness on why it is also beneficial for lecturers to create inclusive education
- Involve lecturers when provisions for neurodiversity and move away from just the academic counselling so that a suitable fit-for-purpose solution for possible challenges for neurodivergent students can be found in which the Learning Objectives combined with the students ability are leading.

